

Transformation 2020 – Team member Publications 2022-2024

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T Cordier, C Corinaldesi, **FO Costa** (2022) Environmental DNA metabarcoding for benthic monitoring: A review of sediment sampling and DNA extraction methods. *Science of The Total Environment*

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